

Preserving the Radburn Gateway Pavilion

Submitted to the Technology Student Association (TSA), 2026.

Raynell Vincent, Ryan Vincent

January 13, 2026

Abstract

This paper examines the Radburn Gateway Pavilion (built in 1929), a fictitious, inspired landmark located in Fair Lawn, NJ, around 1 mile from Fair Lawn High School. This pavilion has undergone significant damage as a result of freeze/thaw cycles, inadequate drainage, and moisture. This has had a very negative impact on the foundation and masonry of the building which poses a significant risk to the safety and preservation of the structure. To mitigate these risks, we have developed a comprehensive plan that utilizes 3 engineering disciplines (civil, structural, and environmental). To determine how significant the damage is, strengthen the weak areas of the building, and coordinate the restoration, modern technologies such as ground-penetrating radar systems, 3D laser scanning, structural health monitoring (SHM) devices, and building information modeling (BIM) are used. To increase the resilience of the pavilion while keeping historical accuracy, sustainable solutions such as some breathable sealants, porous drainage systems, and solar-powered monitoring devices have been added to the design. In order to guarantee safety, functionality, and keep cultural importance, this plan combines both modern technology and sustainable design.

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Introduction and Site Description

The Radburn Gateway Pavilion is a fictitious historically-inspired landmark located in the Radburn neighborhood of Fair Lawn, New Jersey. Radburn is famous for its early suburban and pedestrian-focused design and construction. The pavilion is bordered by residential streets, walking paths, and parkland which makes it in constant association with both society and nature. The climate of Northeastern New Jersey is humid continental. This means that the pavilion is exposed to numerous occasions of bad weather such as snow, heavy rainfall, freezing temperatures, and freeze/thaw cycles every year. These conditions significantly contribute to the degradation of the Radburn Gateway Pavilion, especially the materials it is made out of including older concrete.

The building was constructed in 1929 using reinforced concrete, limestone elements (decorative), and brick masonry. The goal of the pavilion was to serve 2 purposes: as a community gathering place, and as a ceremonial entrance. While the building has endured nearly a century, prolonged exposure to the poor environmental conditions (as mentioned above) and insufficient preservation has left the pavilion in dire need of a comprehensive restoration.

Historical and Cultural Importance

The Radburn Gateway Pavilion has deep cultural significance because it was directly inspired by the Garden City Movement (started in 1898) and its planning philosophies that

transformed suburban development in the 1900s. The pavilion symbolizes a time period when urban development prioritized green space, pedestrian safety, and community connectivity.

Speaking on community connectivity, the pavilion was designed as a community gathering place. People from all parts of Fair Lawn (and nearby towns) could come together and have fun. Considering the fact that the pavilion was constructed in 1929, it has been in Fair Lawn for essentially a century. There are grandparents who remember hanging out in the pavilion when they were kids and now their grandchildren are going and doing the same. The Radburn Gateway Pavilion is a multi-generational landmark that has societal importance to the citizens of Fair Lawn.

Current Risks Threatening the Structure

The pavilion currently faces 2 major risks that threaten its structural integrity and durability. The first major risk is water infiltration which is caused by insufficient drainage and rising groundwater levels. Over many years, moisture has seeped into the foundation and brick masonry of the building, leading to concrete cracking and corrosion of the internal steel reinforcement. This significantly weakens the pavilion and dramatically increases the likelihood of structural failure.

The second major risk is the damage that is caused by freeze/thaw cycles. Water seeps through the brick masonry and concrete and when this water freezes, it expands which causes surface spalling and significant cracking. This continuous cycle over time accelerates the

deterioration of the pavilion and creates safety hazards for the public. If these issues are not addressed, the damage will become irreversible.

Engineering Disciplines Involved in the Restoration

Structural Engineering

Structural engineering plays an essential role in assessing the damage and stabilizing the pavilion. Structural engineers will use ground-penetrating radar systems and 3D laser scanning technology to identify voids, internal cracks/breakage, and areas that hold corroded steel reinforcement that is not visible from the surface. They will also implement structural health monitoring sensors that will track vibration, movement, and stress in the pavilion.

Fiber-reinforced polymer wraps will be applied to reinforce weak areas without changing the pre-existing appearance. This part of the plan will significantly increase the strength and durability of the pavilion without compromising historical accuracy.

Civil Engineering

Civil engineering is essential for addressing the conditions of the site (New Jersey climate) that contribute to the degradation of the pavilion. Insufficient drainage is one of the two major causes of foundation failure. Therefore, civil engineers will redesign the surrounding stormwater management system. This redesign will include underground drainage channels and permeable pavers that will reduce moisture exposure and redirect water away from the pavilion. The engineers will also conduct a LiDAR-based analysis of the site to ensure that the changes

made to the grading to prevent flooding while keeping the original historical appearance.

Environmental Engineering

Environmental engineering also plays an important role in our preservation plan for the Radburn Gateway Pavilion. Environmental engineers will focus their work on material sustainability, moisture control, and environmental impact. They will apply breathable, non-toxic sealants to prevent water intrusion while allowing trapped moisture to escape. They will also select only environmentally friendly and responsible materials in order to reduce long-term environmental harm and align our plan with modern sustainability standards.

Use of Advanced Technologies and Sustainable Systems

Advanced technologies are necessary to ensure the pavilion's preservation because traditional preservation techniques and technologies are insufficient for the problem being addressed. To integrate data from all engineers and allow the team to coordinate the restoration effectively, building information modeling (BIM) will be used. Additionally, solar-powered monitoring systems will give us structural data without affecting energy efficiency. To reduce runoff near the foundation while supporting the original appearance, rainwater collection and redirection systems will be implemented. These modern technologies will preserve the Radburn Gateway Pavilion, keep the original look, and reduce the impacts of the environment onto the pavilion.

Conclusion

Our comprehensive preservation plan for the Radburn Gateway Pavilion shows how modern engineering disciplines and technologies can be utilized to restore historic buildings without losing cultural significance. By focusing on the pavilion's structural integrity, sustainability concerns, and the environmental concerns of existing in New Jersey, we can ensure the safety, longevity, and functionality of the structure. The usage of modern technology and multidisciplinary engineering solutions allows the building to handle future environmental stress while keeping historical and societal relevance. Ultimately, the preservation of the Radburn Gateway Pavilion protects an important symbol of Fair Lawn's history and provides a precedent for future historical preservation.

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Appendix

Figure 1

Caption: Conceptual location of the fictitious Radburn Gateway Pavilion in the area near Archery Plaza within the Radburn neighborhood. This is a strategic location as it emphasizes green space and community gathering.

Figure 2

Caption: The location of the fictitious Radburn Gateway Pavilion in satellite imagery in order to see the terrain.

Table 1

<u>Engineering Discipline</u>	<u>Technology Used</u>	<u>Purpose</u>
Structural	Ground-Penetrating Radars	Detect Internal Voids/Cracks
Structural	SHM Sensors	Monitor Stress + movement
Civil	Permeable Drainage Systems	Reduce Water Infiltration
Environmental	Breathable Sealants	Control Moisture Sustainably
All	BIM	Coordinate Restoration Phases

Table 2

<u>Identified Risks</u>	<u>Engineering Discipline</u>	<u>Mitigation Strategy</u>
Water Infiltration	Civil	Stormwater Redirection + Drainage
Freeze/Thaw Damage	Structural	Masonry Repair + FRP Reinforcement
Long-Term Monitoring	Environmental	Solar-Powered Sensors

Table 3

<u>Phase</u>	<u>Primary Focus</u>	<u>Engineering Disciplines</u>	<u>Key Actions + Technologies</u>	<u>Outcome</u>
1: Assessment + Diagnostics	Identify structural, environmental, and site-related risks	Structural, Civil, Environmental	Ground-penetrating radar, 3D laser scanning, SHM sensors, LiDAR site analysis, moisture assessment	Accurate identification of internal damage, drainage issues, and baseline structural performance
2: Structural Stabilization + Site Improvements	Strengthen structure and reduce environmental stress	Structural, Civil	Masonry repair, crack sealing, fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) reinforcement, permeable paving, subsurface drainage systems	Improved structural integrity, reduced water infiltration, mitigation of freeze/thaw damage
3: Sustainability + Long-Term Monitoring	Enhance resilience and ensure continued performance	Environmental, Structural	Breathable non-toxic sealants, solar-powered monitoring systems, Building Information Modeling (BIM) documentation	Long-term durability, reduced maintenance needs, continuous performance monitoring